

Analysis Errors Committed by Iraqi EFL University Students
in the Area of English Subjunctive

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To my Late Parents with Love and Gratitude...

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Introduction

Subjunctive mood is one of the grammatical devices which shows the manner under which the statement is made (Hartmann and Stork , 1972 :224) .

To trace the traditional meaning from which the word is derived , subjunctive, used in the sense of “ subjoining “ , refers to the link established between the verb form and the speaker’s attitude towards the content of the sentence as a whole (Barhart , 1953) .

Since English and Arabic are two originally unrelated languages , it is expected that there are variations in the use , and realizations of the category of mood . Such variations are expected to affect the performance of Iraqi College students learning English as a foreign language . However , a study is needed to find out whether this expectation is correct or not , and how far the variations affects EFL students' performance .

The study is carried out for the fourth stage of English Department , College of Languages ,University of Baghdad , of Iraqi EFL students to investigate the areas of difficulty on the production level .

The study is believed to be important on both theoretical and practical levels . On the theoretical part , the study investigates the means of wishing , recommending , suggesting ,recommending , doubting , talking about hypothetical situations in English . On the practical part , the study will be of importance to Iraqi foreign students of English who wish to use constructions , syntactically proper in the English language .

The study is significant for teachers to enable them to find a way to present the structure in the classrooms ; and to syllabus – designers as to find a method by which they could present the structure in the text books .

1. Uses of Subjunctive Mood in English

The subjunctive has the following main categories :-

(a) Were – Subjunctive (hypothetical subjunctive) (past or unreal past)

This structure is used in the following contexts :-

(1) In a condition contrary to fact or untrue constructions .

(1) If he were to fall into the pond , he would come up with a fish in his mouth
(Waldhorn and Zeiger , 1954 : 30)

The past subjunctive were is used to convey that the speaker is not sure that the situation will happen or is happening .

With the first and third person singular , and except in formal style , indicative was is used in place of past subjunctive .

(2) If he was to be appointed , I would leave .

(Greenbaum , 1991 :58)

(2) Were - subjunctive is hypothetical in meaning .For this reason , it is used after optative verbs like wish , or suppose , and imagine in the imperative . (Quirk et al.,1985:1013) .

(3) Were – subjunctive is used in inverted subject order to substitute for a deleted conditional if . The example explains the above :

(3) Were – it to reveal its secrets, that house would collapse in shame (ibid.)

(4) Were – subjunctive is used after as if , as though , even if , to indicate unreality , improbability , or doubt in the present .

(4) He behaves as if he owned the place (but he does not own it , or probably does not own it , or we don't know whether he owns it or not) .

Past perfect is used when referring to a real or imaginary action in the past

(5) He talks / talked about Rome as though he had been there himself (But he hasn't or probably hasn't or we don't know whether he has or not) .

The verb preceding as if / as though can be put in a past tense without changing the tense of the subjunctive . (Thomson and Martinet , 1986:245) .

(5) Past Subjunctive is used after it is time .

(6) It is time we went / we were leaving .

The past subjunctive means that it is a little late . High can be added to emphasize this idea .

(7) It's high time we left .

Only you and we can be followed by were , while I/he/she/it cannot .

(8) It is time I was going (Thomson and Martinet , 1986:254) .

(b) Mandative Subjunctive , i.e. the subjunctive used in that – constructions after verbs , nouns , or adjective which denote asking , agreeing , demanding , determining , directing , enacting , insisting , ordering , proposing , recommending , suggesting , and the like .

(9) He moved that the meeting be adjourned .

(10) It is necessary that the justice be done (Waldhorn and Zeiger ,1954:30) .

For verbs other than be , the present subjunctive has the base form ending in- s . In other singular forms , and in plurals , the base form is the same as the present tense form .

(11) We demand that they take the witness stand. (Greenbaum ,1991:58) .

However , there is no back shifting of tense , i.e. the present and past variants are indistinguishable .

(12) The committee $\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{proposes} \\ \text{proposed} \end{array} \right\}$ (that) Mr. Day be elected .

The verb in the superordinate clause takes the form of a verb , an adjective , or a noun.

- (13) $\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{They recommended} \\ \text{It is appropriate} \\ \text{We were faced with} \\ \text{the demand} \end{array} \right\}$ that this tax be abolished (Quirk et al,1985:165)

In factive that – clause , i.e. insert sentences , the mandative subjunctive functions as object . (Thomas,1965:200) .

- (14) I prefer that Roger go (Fries ,1940 :107) .

There are certain verbs that are followed by should + infinitive constructions . When the infinitive is be , should is sometimes omitted .

- (15) He suggested that a petition (should) be drawn up . (Thomson and Martinet,1986 :253) .

For all persons , the negative need not have an operator .

- (16) We demand that $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{he} \\ \text{they} \end{array} \right\}$ not take the witness stand . (Greenbaum ,1991:59)

(c) Formulaic Subjunctive

This type persists in many idioms , formulae and fossilized expressions .

- (17) Far be it from me .

- (18) Peace be with you .

- (19) Though he stay , yet I will trust in him .
(Waldhorn and Zeiger , 1954 :30)

This type expresses wish , hope and very often involves supernatural powers.

God (bless you) ! (Strang , 1968 :153).

1.1 Verbs in the Matrix Clause that Govern Subjunctive Verbs

Two classes of verbs in the matrix clause can be distinguished :-

(1) Suasive Verbs , e.g. suggest that imply intentions to bring about some change in the future , whether or not these are verbally formulated , as commands, suggestions . These verbs can be followed by that –clauses with should , or with mandative subjunctive verb . (Quirk et al.,1985:1180) .

The particle that in that – clauses that functions as object may be deleted .

(20) I suggest he go now .

However , that is obligatory when the clause is passive as that – clause would be the passive subject . That is optional when that – clause is extraposed and the whole sentence is introduced by it .

(21) a. I suggest (that) he go .

b. That he go was suggested .

c. It was suggested (that) he go (ibid. :1179) .

(2) Hypotheses verbs, e.g. wish , introduce that - clause of which verb phrase is hypothetical past (were - subjunctive) .

(22) Suppose (that) one of us died .

(23) I'd rather you didn't mention the price .

(24) Many residents would rather that the bus service were subsidized .(ibid.:1183) .

1.2 Functions of Subjunctive

Subjunctive has two main functions : the optative and potential .

Optative marks something as desired , demanded , or requested whether by a person or by a certain circumstance . (Curme, 1935:224-7) .

(25) May you say many returns of the occasion .

(26) I insist that I be given a new assignment (Strang ,1968 :153) .

Potential represents something as a mere conception of the mind , that may possibly or probably become realizable or unrealizable .

(27) If he confess , I shall overlook the offence .

The conditional clause , have , is used to express possibility or likelihood. (op.cit.)

(28) If he were my friend , he would speak for my cause .

Were –subjunctive is used to express hypotheses (Leech ,1971:106) .

2 . The Test

This study is based on completion test given to sixty students of the fourth year of English Department , College of Languages , University of Baghdad . The test consists of fifteen items covering the three types of English Subjunctive Constructions (See Appendix) .

2 .1 Description of the Test

The test is divided into three parts: the first of which deals with were or hypothetical past subjunctive . The students are asked to give the correct form of the verbs in brackets .

The second part consists of mandative subjunctive . It aims at measuring the students' productive knowledge of the form of verb in the subordinate clause .

The third part is devoted to measuring the students' performance on the formulaic subjunctive .

The items of the test has been designed to serve the following purposes .

1. Items 1 and 2 have been designed to see whether students are aware of the hypothetical meaning of the forms of the subjunctive .
2. Items 3,4 and 5 find out whether students produce verbs in the subjunctive mood after wish , suppose , or I'd rather .
3. Items 6 and 7 find out whether students can produce verbs in the base form after he without should , or without s .
4. Item 8 aims at finding out whether students :
 - a. Can produce the correct form of the verbs, i.e. the base form ,
 - b. Can produce the particle not in the correct position,
 - c. Can produce the form of the subjunctive verb after adjectives that give the meaning of obligation , intention , etc .
5. Item 9 finds out whether students :
 - a.Can produce the correct verb form after declared , and
 - b.Can place not before or after the verb in the subjunctive .
6. Item 10 aims at finding out whether students are aware of the fact that the noun demand has the force on the verb in the subordinate clause to be in the base form .
7. Items 11 ,13 and 14 find out whether students can use the subjunctive verb form before it , i.e. in the inverted word- order structure .
8. Items 12 and 15 measure the students' awareness of using subjunctive in such forms .

2.2 Discussion of Results

In this section , the subjects' performance on the item tests will be presented and the possible reasons behind the incorrect responses will be stated .

1. Fifty – one students, i.e. 85 % out of the total number of students' responses to the item were correct in answering item 1. The same number of students were correct in answering item 2 .

This results from the fact that students are quite acquainted with this structure in their textbooks for much emphasis is paid for the second case of if – clauses : the hypothetical if . Context of learning is the factor to which the correct responses may be ascribed.

Positive interlingual transfer may be a second factor , for the same structure is realized in Arabic in that the past tense should be used after the particle لو / law / إذا / or if (see Schachter and Celce – Murica ,1980:127 ; Brown, 1987:179). Some errors are ascribed to poor gradation of teaching items .

2. Forty-five students answered item 3 correctly, i.e. 75 % out of the total number of responses to this item . This may be attributed , again, to context of learning , for emphasis is laid on this structure , Students are aware that wish should introduce verbs in the past forms (ibid.) .

3.Ten students out of the total number of students were correct in performing on item 4 , i.e. 17 % out of the total number of responses to this item . The students are not acquainted with the fact that after suppose , verbs should be in the past .

Being unaware of the hypothetical meaning of suppose , the students overgeneralize the rule of using present tense after suppose .

4. Forty students answered item 5 correctly, i.e. 67 % out of the total number of responses to the item . They are acquainted with the fact that after I'd rather , the verb in the clause should be in the past tense . Context of Learning is responsible for their correct responses (see ibid. :127).

5. Concerning item 6 , thirty-five students ,i.e. 59 % out of the total number of responses to the item answered the item correctly . They used was or should be instead of be or were . They are familiar with the fact that after these verbs , the subjunctive verb should be used (Context of Learning) .

6. For item 7 , forty students answered the item correctly , i.e. 67 % out of the total number of responses to the item . This is due to context of learning for emphasis is

laid upon the fact that verbs like suggest should be following by subjunctive verb (Context of Learning) .

7. For item 8 , thirty-two students ,i.e. 57 % out of the total number of responses to the item , were correct in answering the item . The erroneous responses are due to the fact that students are unaware of the fact that adjectives may introduce subjunctive verbs .

Consequently , their answer was dose not fail . They are unaware , that not could precede the base verb form fail . These errors are attributed to ignorance of rule restrictions , where the learner is making use of a rule he has learned before in a new situation (Richards,1974:174) . His application of the rule , however , is not correct .

8. Thirty-five students , i.e. 59 % out of the total number of responses to item 9 answered the item correctly . Students' answer was were not . The correct answer is be not or not be . They were not aware of the structure (Context of Learning) (ibid. :180) .

9. Thirty-two students, i.e. 57 % out of the total number of answers to the item , answered item 10 correctly as they are unaware of the force the noun has on the verb in the subordinate clause . The correct answer should be be (Ignorance of rule restrictions) (ibid. :174) .

10. Eight students answered item 11 correctly , i.e. 14 % out of the total number of responses to the item , for they are quite unaware of the inverted word-order structure , and of the form of the whole sentence . The same number of students answered item 13 for the same reason (Ignorance of rule restrictions) .

11. Seven students answered item 12 , i.e. 12 % out of the total number of responses to the item . They overgeneralize the rule and wrote it as blessees or should bless . They are again unaware of the form . The same number of students answered item 15 (ibid. :193) .

12. Concerning item 14 , thirty-nine students , i.e. 65 % out of the total number of responses to the item answered the item correctly , and they use come as an imperative verb . They are unaware that come should preceded by what / may . Again , they are not familiar with this structure (Ignorance of rule restrictions) (ibid. : 174) .

Table-1 Students' Responses to the Items of the Test

Item No.	No. of Correct Responses	Percentage of Correct Responses	No. of Erroneous Responses	Percentage of Erroneous Responses
1	51	85	9	15
2	51	85	9	15
3	45	75	15	25
4	10	17	50	83
5	40	67	20	33
6	35	59	25	41
7	40	67	20	33
8	32	57	28	43
9	35	75	15	25
10	32	57	28	43
11	8	14	52	86
12	7	12	53	88
13	8	14	52	86
14	39	65	21	35
15	7	12	53	88

3. Conclusion

As English and Arabic differ in expressing subjunctive , it is expected that difficulties are felt on the part of Iraqi EFL students in producing the structure .

This , the study finds out that these differences cause difficulties manifested by Iraqi EFL students' responses to the test items .

The results of the study , furthermore , indicate that overgeneralization , ignorance of rule restrictions , and textbooks , context of learning are the main factors that account for the errors committed in this area .

Non-correspondence of English and Arabic subjunctive mood makes it important to realize that interlingual transfer , i.e. errors caused by negative transfer from the mother tongue which impedes the learning or has negative influence on it (Els et al. ,1984:49) does not contribute much to these errors .

It has been ,furthermore , proved that most errors are made on formulaic subjunctive. This is because mandative subjunctive is mastered by them in the course of learning complementation , or reported speech . The same is true with conditional or unreal past subjunctive for this has been explained , along with conditional clauses . This is indicated by the results as it is obvious that they mastered unreal past that has been widely , and repeatedly explained in conditional clauses . This should go better than mastering mandative subjunctive , explained in the course of presenting complementation and reported speech . For the latter , they may commit errors as the structure requiress less verb form with the third person singular .

No such presentation has been devoted to formulaic expressions used widely in formal language .

This necessities that the textbook designer emphasize on this type , design more exercises ; and the teacher train students to use this structure .

It should , furthermore , be recommended that much emphasis be paid on subjunctive . The use of this structure in formal (legal) language makes it important to deal with subjunctive as a living structure .

Textbook designers should devote much space , emphasis and exercises that deal with the types and function of subjunctive so as students would get the chance to understand this structure .

Appendix – The Test

Supply the correct form of the verbs in brackets of the following sentences :-

0. If the earth -----flat , men could perhaps sail asquare it . (to be)
1. If wishes ----- horses , beggars would ride (to be) .
2. I wish ----- your widow (to be) .
3. Suppose we ----- her the truth (tell) .
4. I'd rather we ----- dinner now (have) .
5. They proposed formally that he ---- admitted (to be) .
6. I suggest that the student ---- carefully the nature of mood (to consider) .
7. It is essential that this mission not ----- (fail) .
8. The senate has declared that such students not ----- exempted from college duties (to be) .
9. We were faced with the demand that this tax ---- abolished (to be) .
10. Far ---- it from me to split infinitives, or hairs ; to dangle participles or babies ; to modify substantives or opinions (to be) .
11. God ----- you (bless) .
12. Long ----- the president (live) .
13. ----- what may , we will go ahead with our plan (come) .
14. Heaven ----- that I shall let my own parents suffer (forbid) .

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